

Spectrophotometric Method for the Determination of some Thioamino Acids and Thioureas in Pure and Pharmaceutical Preparations

AJAYA PRAKASH, A. P. SINGH and I. C. SHUKLA*

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad,
Allahabad-211 002Manuscript received 11 May 1983, revised 24 April 1986,
accepted 9 March 1987

THIOAMINO acids have a great medicinal value, therefore their determination has been extensively attempted. Many volumetric¹ and spectrophotometric² methods have been proposed for the estimation of small amounts of thioamino acids. McCarthy and Sullivan³ described the determination of methionine with the use of sodium nitroprusside solution, which cannot be applied for the determination of acetylmethionine, cysteine and cystine. A specific colorimetric method has been reported by Maugenet *et al.*⁴ extending the method of McCarthy and Paille⁵, for the estimation of methionine in yeasts. The method described in the present paper has been developed as a general procedure for the determination of thioamino acids and thioureas on microgram scale.

Experimental

All the reagents were of AnalaR grade. Stock solutions of sodium nitroprusside (10.0%, w/v), potassium ferricyanide (10.0%, w/v), sodium hydroxide (10.0%, w/v) were prepared in double-distilled CO₂-free water and stored in ambered bottles.

Preparation of oxidised nitroprusside reagent: Equal volume of sodium nitroprusside (10.0%), potassium ferricyanide (10.0%) and sodium hydroxide (10.0%) solutions were mixed in the order mentioned. The mixture was shaken thoroughly and allowed to stand at room temperature. After about 30 min the red colour of the solution changed to yellow. The solution was used for developing colour with thioaminoacids and thioureas. In each experiments a freshly prepared solution of the reagent was used.

Sample solution: Methionine, acetylmethionine and cysteine hydrochloride (100 mg) were dissolved in distilled water in 100 ml calibrated volumetric flasks. Cystine (100 mg) was first dissolved in 1N HCl (5 ml) and then the volume was made upto the mark with distilled water in a 100 ml calibrated volumetric flask. Thiourea, allyl thiourea and phenyl thioureas were dissolved in distilled water.

Apparatus: Absorbance measurements were carried out with a Beckman DB spectrophotometer using 1/2 cm matched silica cells.

Preparation of standard curve: In case of methionine and acetyl methionine, the sample solutions were diluted and the aliquots containing

20–160 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of the sample were transferred to different 25 ml calibrated volumetric flasks. Oxidized nitroprusside reagent (2.0 ml) was then added to it, contents shaken and the flasks were placed on a water-bath at 37° for 15 min. After the reaction was over the flasks were removed from the water-bath and cooled to room temperature (27°). To each flask 5.0% sulphuric acid (4 ml) was added, contents were shaken thoroughly and diluted up to the mark with distilled water. After allowing the flask to stand for 15 min, a red colour developed which was stable for 1 h. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 500 nm.

For cysteine hydrochloride and cystine (40–240 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) samples were treated similarly in a 25 ml calibrated volumetric flask and heated at 37° on a water-bath for 45 min. After cooling the flask to room temperature, 5.0% sulphuric acid (9.0 ml) was added. The contents were shaken thoroughly and diluted upto the mark with distilled water. After

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF PURE THIOAMINO ACIDS AND THIOUREAS

Sl. no.	Sample	Amount taken μg	Estimated* amount μg	Amount obtained by recovery experiment %	Error %
1.	Methionine	20	20.12	100.30	+0.60
		40	40.18	100.45	+0.45
		60	59.94	99.97	-0.10
		80	80.23	100.24	+0.29
		100	99.96	100.02	-0.04
		120	119.92	99.86	-0.06
2.	Acetyl methionine	140	141.03	100.83	+0.73
		20	20.09	100.34	+0.45
		60	60.24	100.57	+0.40
		80	79.87	99.88	-0.16
		100	100.08	99.95	+0.08
		120	100.78	100.84	+0.60
3.	Cysteine hydrochloride	140	139.87	99.73	-0.10
		160	159.72	100.25	-0.17
		100	99.84	99.76	-0.16
		140	139.67	99.68	-0.23
		180	180.92	100.87	+0.51
4.	Cystine	220	221.74	101.32	+0.79
		240	241.08	100.52	+0.45
		40	40.08	100.09	+0.20
		80	79.79	99.82	-0.10
		120	119.95	99.73	-0.29
5.	Thiourea	160	160.82	101.20	+0.51
		200	200.43	100.30	+0.21
		6	5.96	—	-0.66
		22	22.96	—	-0.27
		40	39.80	—	-0.50
6.	Allyl thiourea	12	11.96	—	-0.33
		20	19.82	—	-0.99
		44	48.68	—	-0.72
7.	Phenyl thiourea	80	79.62	—	-0.47
		140	139.40	—	-0.43
		200	198.84	—	0.58

*Average of three experiments.

TABLE 2—ESTIMATION OF METHIONINE AND ACETYLMETHIONINE IN COMMERCIAL SAMPLES AND ITS RECOVERY

Sl. no.	Sample*	Label claim mg	Estimated* amount by proposed method mg	Estimated** amount by standard method mg	% recovery** by the proposed method	% Error
1.	(A)	500 mg/Γ	497.50	495.8	99.20	-0.5
2.	(A, P ₁ , P ₂ , D, I, C ₁)	32 mg/T	32.23	32.30	100.03	+0.71
3.	(A, C ₁ , I, B _{1,2} , L)	110 mg/C	109.00	108.32	99.78	-0.90
4.	(A, C ₁ , I, B _{1,2} , L)	350 mg/15 ml	352.50	-	102.00	+0.71
5.	(B, T ₁ , B _{1,2} , I)	1220 mg/15 ml	1230.00	-	101.40	+0.81
6.	(B, C ₁ , I, K, Kh)	325 mg/5 ml	327.50	-	99.63	+0.76
7.	(B, C ₁ , K, Kh, S, P ₁)	150 mg/15 ml	149.20	-	100.80	-0.53

*A - methionine, B - acetylmethionine, P₁ - pepsin, P₂ - pepain, D - diastase, I - inositol, C₁ - choline dihydrogen citrate, B_{1,2} - vitamin B_{1,2}, L - liver concentrate, T₁ - tricholine citrate, K - Kalmegh, Kh - Khetpara, S - sodium tauroglycocholate.

15 min, a green colour was obtained which was stable for 2 h. The absorbance of the coloured solution was measured at 680 nm (for cysteine hydrochloride) and 660 nm (for cystine). A graph for absorbance vs concentration was plotted in all the cases. A blank experiment was also performed.

Analysis of commercial samples: The proposed method was applied for the determination of methionine and acetyl methionine in capsules, tablets and syrups. Results of the present method were compared with the standard method⁶. Twenty tablets or capsules as the case might be weighed, powdered and powder equivalent to 100 mg of pure sample was weighed and dissolved in distilled water and filtered. The volume of the filtrate was adjusted to 100 ml in a calibrated volumetric flask and the assay was carried out following the procedure as described for constructing the standard curve. The amount of the sample was calculated from the standard graph. In case of penzime tablet (no. 2, Table 2), the powder was treated with charcoal and filtered. Aliquots of syrups equivalent to 100 mg of pure sample were transferred to 100 ml volumetric flasks and volume adjusted with distilled water.

To justify the suitability of the proposed method, known amount of pure sample was added to the previously analysed drug sample and then assayed again. The recovery values obtained were between 99 to 102%.

For thioureas, aliquots containing 2-250 µg of the sample were transferred into 25 ml calibrated volumetric flask. Oxidized nitroprusside reagent (2 ml) was added to each flask, contents were shaken and diluted upto the mark with distilled water. Thiourea and allylthiourea gave orange red and green colour, respectively, after 3 h, the

colour being stable for 5 h. Phenylthiourea gave yellow green colour after 5 min, the colour being stable for 0.5 h. Absorbance of the colour developed was measured at 524 nm (thiourea), 580 nm (allylthiourea) and 450 nm (phenylthiourea).

The results obtained with pure samples and pharmaceutical preparations are recorded in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The formation of different colours in the reaction is believed to be due to the complex formation between the oxidised state of the reagent and the compound. None of the compounds gave any colour either with ferricyanide or nitroprusside alone. Although the heating of the reaction mixture quickens the development of the colour but the oxidised nitroprusside reagent gets precipitated giving inaccurate results.

The presence of urea, glycine, alanine, L-asparagine, chloroacetic acid and acetone do not interfere, while the presence of methanol streptomycin sulphate, formaldehyde and a solution of sodium chloride or sodium sulphate in excess of 0.5% interfere. The presence of glucose, galactose and lactose give unstable colour and do not change the validity of Beer - Lambert law. In pharmaceutical preparations, the presence of malt extract interfere. Thiourea and allyl thiourea can not be estimated in a mixture but either of them can be estimated in the presence of phenylthiourea. The method has also been tried with respect to decomposition of the drug in samples stored for different time intervals. It is found that in case of methionine and acetyl methionine, 10% of the drug is decomposed after 24 months.

References

1. I. STOIAN and R. CRACIUNEANU, *Rev. Chem. (Bucharest)*, 1979, 30, 383; E. G. TROUT, *Anal. Biochem.*, 1979, 93, 419; N. M. M. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Talanta*, 1977, 24, 470; M. M. BEG, Q. S. USMANI and I. C. SHUKLA, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1977, 2, 222.
2. L. H. KRULL, D. E. GIBBS and M. FRIEDMANN, *Anal. Biochem.*, 1971, 40, 48; B. JASELSKI and D. S. SCHOUGH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1974, 46, 7; M. N. BEG, F. A. SIDDIQUI, M. M. BEG, R. SHYAM and M. ARSHAD, *Analyst*, 1979, 104, 977; M. TONKOVIC and O. HADZIA, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1977, 2, 241; KRISHNASWAMY, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1942 36, 4058.
3. M. MCCARTHY and M. K. SULLIVAN, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1941, 141, 871.
4. J. L. MAUGNET, H. MARIA and M. L. DALMEYDA, *Annals Technol. Agric.*, 1972, 21, 73.
5. M. MCCARTHY and A. PAILLE, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, 1959, 1, 29.
6. "The United States Pharmacopoea XX and the National Formulary XV", Supplement, 1980, Vol. 1, p. 48.